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Assessment Of Teachers' Use Of Innovative Teaching Strategies And Content Coverage In Basic Science And Technology Curriculum Implementation In Upper Basic Schools

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed teachers' use of innovative teaching strategies and content coverage in Basic Science and Technology (BST) curriculum implementation in upper basic schools in North Central Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design with a population of 4,026 Basic Science and Technology teachers in public upper basic schools, out of which a sample of 386 Basic science and technology teachers were selected using multistage sampling. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire designed by the researchers titled Teachers use of Innovative Teaching Strategies and Content Coverage in Basic Science and Technology Curriculum Implementation Questionnaire (TUITSCCBSTQ), validated by experts with a reliability coefficient of 0.89. The data collected were analysed using mean, standard deviation, and Mann-Whitney U test at 0.05 level of significance. The finding of the study revealed that teachers commonly used instructional strategies such as active learning, cooperative learning, demonstration, problem-based learning, and team teaching. The findings also showed that there was an adequate level of curriculum content coverage in upper basic schools, with no significant difference between urban and rural teachers. However, there was a significant difference between urban and rural teachers regarding the use of innovative teaching methods. It was recommended that educational authorities should ensure regular training, adequate supervision, and equal resource provision to enhance teachers' adoption of innovative strategies across all locations.

Keywords: Innovative Teaching Strategies, Content Coverage, Curriculum Implementation, Basic Science and Technology, Upper Basic Schools

INTRODUCTION

Basic Science and Technology is a foundational subject in Nigeria's upper basic education curriculum, designed to equip students with scientific knowledge, technological skills, and problem-solving competencies essential for national development and participation in the global knowledge economy. The Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2012) revised the Basic Science and Technology curriculum to reflect the needs of the 21st century, emphasizing the use of learner-centered teaching approach, practical activities, critical thinking, and integration of digital technologies. These reforms are aligned with international best practices in STEM education and aim to move classroom instruction away from rote memorization towards inquiry-driven and experiential learning.

According to Mohammed and Dajal (2024) innovative teaching strategy is one that emphasizes learner-centered and activity-based instruction. Innovative teaching strategies includes activity-based learning, problem-solving strategies, inquiry-based approaches, cooperative learning, and the integration of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) have been widely recognized for their ability to improve students' attitude, interest and achievement in science subjects (Oribhabor, 2020; Dajal, Mohammed and Oguntade, 2024). These methods are grounded in constructivist theories that prioritize active learner participation, making them essential tools for the effective implementation of the BST curriculum.

However, for the objectives of BST curriculum to be achieved, teachers must not only adopt innovative instructional strategies but also ensure adequate coverage of the curriculum content. The level of content coverage refers to the extent to which teachers are able to teach the breadth and depth of topics stipulated in the BST curriculum within the available instructional time. Content coverage is essential implementation variable because Insufficient or inadequate coverage of content might impede students' comprehension and preparedness for further scientific study. Studies indicates that inadequate subject coverage, frequently resulting from inflexible teaching methods, inadequate instructional planning, or time constraints, may undermine curricular efficacy, even when new pedagogical approaches are used (Nwosu, Etiubon, & Ofem, 2023).

The availability of resources, teacher competence and infrastructural development is different in the schools that are within the study area. These differences call for the need to investigate the teachers use of innovative teaching strategy and well as the level of content coverage in Basic Science and Technology curriculum implementation. This study therefore assessed teachers use of innovative teaching strategy and well as the level of content coverage in Basic Science and Technology curriculum implementation in upper basic schools in North Central Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The Basic Science and Technology (BST) curriculum in Nigeria offers innovative and student-centered pedagogy, yet in many upper basic schools in North Central Nigeria, the curriculum is still mostly implemented by teachers. Education is often focused on texts, memorisation, and little contact between the instructor and students (Ibrahim & Abubakar, 2023). This reduces motivation and inhibits the development of practical skills and scientific thinking. The curriculum implementation depends on the degree of utilization of innovative teaching strategies and the level of content coverage the levels to which the teachers can address the recommended content. However, when the use of new practices and time management is not sufficient, the topics may tend to be covered hurriedly or incompletely, which may affect the knowledge and readiness of the students to further study science (Nwosu, Etiubon, & Ofem, 2023). The studies also reveal that a majority of teachers are struggling to embrace the use of innovative teaching strategies because of their large classes, inadequate instructional resources, and proper training (Oribhabor, 2020). Another issue particularly in regard to rural schools is availability of instructional resources in particular the laboratories and power, which limits ICT-based and practical instructions (Ibrahim and Abubakar, 2023). It is based on this problem that the study therefore, investigated teachers use of innovative teaching strategy and level of content coverage in Basic Science and Technology curriculum implementation in upper basic schools in North Central Nigeria

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine teachers' level of utilization of innovative teaching strategies and content coverage for the implementation of the Basic Science and Technology curriculum in upper basic Schools in North-Central, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to;

- i. determine the common teaching methods used by teachers for implementation of Basic Science and Technology curriculum in Upper Basic Schools in North Central, Nigeria;
- ii. find out the common teaching methods used by teachers for implementation of Basic Science and Technology curriculum in Upper Basic Schools based on location.
- iii. determine the level of coverage of the contents of Basic Science and Technology curriculum in Upper Basic Schools in North Central Nigeria;
- iv. ascertain the difference in the level of coverage of the contents of Basic Science and Technology curriculum in Upper Basic Schools based on location;

Research Questions

1. What are the common teaching methods used by teachers for the implementation of Basic Science and Technology curriculum in Upper Basic Schools in North Central Nigeria?
2. What is the mean difference in the teaching method used by teachers for the implementation of Basic Science and Technology curriculum in Upper Basic Schools based on location?
3. What is the level of coverage of the content of the Basic Science and Technology curriculum by teachers in Upper Basic Schools in North Central Nigeria?
4. What is the difference in the level of coverage of the content of Basic Science and Technology curriculum by teachers in Upper Basic Schools based on location?

Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Basic Science and Technology teachers regarding the level of curriculum coverage content of Basic Science and Technology for implementation in Upper Basic Schools North central Nigeria based on location.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Basic Science and Technology teachers regarding the common teaching methods used for curriculum implementation in Upper Basic Schools in North central Nigeria based on location.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive survey research design. Descriptive survey according to Nwogu (2015), refers to a design in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group or population. The population of this study was 4, 026 Basic Science and Technology teachers in public Upper Basic Schools in North Central Nigeria. A Sample size of three hundred and eighty-six (386) respondents formed the sample of this study. Multi stage sampling procedure was adopted in selection of the sample size. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire designed by researcher titled: Assessment of utilization of innovative teaching strategies and level of content coverage for implementation of Basic Science and Technology Curriculum Questionnaire. The instrument was divided into two (2) sections, A and B. Section A sought information on personal data of the respondents such as gender, location and educational qualification, while section B consists of check list which were divided into two clusters, cluster I contains 26 items on level of coverage of the Basic Science and Technology curriculum Contents and cluster I comprises of 17 statements on method of teaching Basic science in implementing Basic Science and Technology Curriculum. A four-point modified rating scale is used for Cluster I which were Frequently Used (FU=4), Moderately Used (MU=3), Rarely Used (RU=2), Not Used (NU) and Cluster II, which is Adequately Covered (AC = 4), Moderately Covered (MC= 3), Rarely Covered (RAC = 2), Not Covered (NC = 1) The instrument was validated by two experts, one expert was from Department of Science and Environmental Education, University of Abuja, one from Department of Science and Technology Education, Federal University of Technology Minna . The experts' corrections and suggestions were used in the final production of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was determined, by conducting a pilot test using thirty (30) Basic Science and Technology teachers in the schools that had similar characteristics with the sample of this study. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha statistics which yielded reliability index of 0.89. The questionnaires were administered by the researchers, and research assistants to the respondents to fill and return on the spot to avoid loss of the questionnaire. The data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequency count and percentage to analyse bio- data of respondents, mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while for the inferential statistics, the null hypotheses were tested using independent Mann-Whitney U test statistics at 0.05 significant level.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What are the common teaching methods used by teachers for the implementation of Basic Science and Technology curriculum in Upper Basic Schools in North Central Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on level of Utilization of Different Teaching Method used by Teachers for the Implementation of Basic Science and Technology Curriculum in Upper Basic schools in North Central Nigeria N=386

S/N	Teaching Method	Mean	SD	Dec
1	Active learning strategy	3.19	1.06	MU
2	Brain storming	2.60	0.52	MU
3	Computer animation	2.45	0.49	MU
4	Computer assisted learning	2.44	0.52	MU
5	Concept Mapping	3.00	0.00	MU
6	Cooperative learning	3.89	0.42	FU
7	Demonstration	3.88	0.42	FU
8	Discovery method	3.43	0.51	MU
9	Discussion method	3.85	0.53	FU
10	Filed trip/excursion method	3.08	0.92	MU
11	Guided inquiry method	2.53	0.53	MU
12	Lecture	3.03	0.98	MU
13	Problem based learning	3.43	0.61	FU
14	Project based learning method	3.08	1.08	MU
15	Role play method	2.50	0.57	MU
16	Simulation game method	2.48	0.56	MU
17	Team-teaching method	3.39	0.59	FU
18	Use of Analogy	2.74	0.83	MU
	Sectional Mean	2.74	0.99	MU

The analysis on table 1 indicated a mean score of level of utilization of different teaching method was 2.74 with standard deviation of 0.99. This shows that the common teaching method used by basic science and technology teachers for the implementation of Basic Science and Technology curriculum were: active learning strategy, brainstorming, concept mapping, cooperative learning, demonstration, discovery method, discussion method, field trip/excursion method, lecture, problem based learning, role play team teaching, guided discovery, project based learning method, team-teaching method and use of analogy.

Research Question Two: *What are the common teaching methods used by teachers for the implementation of Basic Science and Technology curriculum in Upper Basic Schools based on location?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on Level of Utilization of Different Teaching Method used between Urban and Rural Basic Science and Technology Teachers N=386

S/N	Teaching Method	Urban N=231			Rural N= 155		
		Mean	SD	Dec	Mean	SD	Dec
1	Active learning strategy	3.59	0.81	FU	2..60	0.12	MU
2	Brain storming	2.88	0.32	MU	2.19	2.48	RU
3	Computer animation	2.12	0.32	RU	2.95	0.20	MU
4	Computer assisted learning	2.12	0.32	RU	2.92	0.38	MU
5	Concept Mapping	3.00	0.00	MU	3.00	0.00	MU
6	Cooperative learning	3.91	0.28	FU	3.86	0.58	FU
7	Demonstration	3.91	0.28	FU	3.83	0.58	FU
8	Discovery method	3.12	0.32	MU	3.91	0.34	FU

9	Discussion method	3.83	0.45	FU	3.84	0.63	FU
10	Filed trip/excursion	2.62	0.78	MU	3.78	0.61	FU
11	Guided inquiry method	2.89	0.33	MU	2.01	0.30	RU
12	Lecture	3.68	0.67	FU	2.08	0.43	RU
13	Problem based learning	3.68	0.67	FU	2.19	0.45	RU
14	Project based learning	3.68	0.67	FU	2.19	0.95	RU
15	Role play method	2.21	0.41	RU	2.95	0.48	MU
16	Simulation game method	2.21	0.41	RU	2.91	0.48	MU
17	Team-teaching method	3.14	0.34	MU	3.79	0.68	FU
18	Use of Analogy	2.83	0.82	MU	2.61	0.84	MU
	Sectional Mean	3.08	0.10	MU	3.01	0.18	MU

The analysis on Table 2 showed both urban and rural teachers had a sectional mean of 3.08 and 3.01 respectively. This revealed that the common teaching method used by both urban and rural teachers of basic science and technology was moderately utilized. However, urban teachers had 3.91 mean scores on items 7 and 8 cooperative learning and demonstration as the most common teaching methods used and 2.12 on item 15 and 16 computer animation and computer-assisted learning as the least method used. Rural teachers on the other hand, had mean score of 3.91 on item 8 discovery method as the most common teaching method used and mean score of 2.01 on item 11 guided inquiry as the least common teaching method used. Therefore, both urban and rural teachers commonly use methods such as concept mapping, cooperative learning, demonstration, discovery, discussion, team-teaching, and analogy, suggesting a shared commitment to active and student-centered learning strategies in the implementation of the Basic Science and Technology.

Research Question Three: *What is the level of coverage of the content of the Basic Science and Technology curriculum by teachers in Upper Basic Schools in North Central Nigeria?*

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on Level of Coverage of the Content of Basic Science and Technology Curriculum in Upper Basic in North Central Nigeria N= 386

S/N	Basic Science Content	Mean	SD	DEC
1	Family Health & Environmental pollution.	3.84	0.44	AC
2	Living and Non-living things	3.95	0.31	AC
3	Energy	3.88	0.42	AC
4	Renewable and Non-Renewable Energy	3.95	0.26	AC
5	Understanding technology	3.97	0.20	AC
6	Safety guide line and workshop safety	3.81	0.57	AC
7.	Properties of materials and building material	3.28	0.55	MC
8	Drawing instrument and materials	3.28	0.45	MC
9	Board practice is and wood work tools	3.18	0.51	MC
10	Maintenance of tools and machine	3.24	0.42	MC
11	Forces	3.29	0.46	MC
12.	Chemicals	3.25	0.45	MC
13.	Work, Energy and Power	3.42	0.80	MC
14.	Types of Energy	3.96	0.18	AC
15.	Thermal Energy	3.96	0.18	AC
16.	Light Energy	3.96	1.58	AC
17.	Crude oil and Petrochemicals	2.56	0.96	AC
18.	Family traits	2.99	0.28	MC
19.	Environmental Hazards I,II and III	3.00	0.20	MC
20.	Drug and substance abuse	3.70	0.49	AC
21.	Resources from living things	3.46	0.74	MC
22.	Resources from non-living things	2.81	0.55	MC
23.	Sound Energy	3.08	0.29	MC
24.	Magnetism	2.83	0.58	MC
25.	Electrical Energy	3.08	0.33	MC
26.	Radioactivity	3.07	0.33	MC
27	Science and Development	2.79	0.55	MC
Sectional Mean		3.52	0.50	AC

The analysis on table 3 indicated a sectional mean score of 3.52 with standard deviation of 0.50. This indicated that there is adequate level of coverage of the content of Basic Science and technology curriculum in Upper Basic Schools in North Central Nigeria.

Research Question Four: *What is the mean difference in the level of coverage of the content of Basic Science and Technology curriculum by teachers in Upper Basic Schools based on location?*

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation on Level of Coverage of the Content of Basic Science and Technology Curriculum by Urban and Rural Basic Science and Technology Teachers N=386

S/N	Basic Science Content	Urban n= 231			Rural n= 155		
		Mean	SD	DEC	Mean	SD	DEC
1	Family Health & Environmental pollution.	3.89	0.30	AC	3.76	0.58	AC
2	Living and Non-living things	3.99	0.06	AC	3.90	0.49	AC
3	Energy	3.97	0.15	AC	3.76	0.62	AC
4	Renewable and Non-Renewable Energy	3.99	0.06		3.89	0.39	AC
5	Understanding technology	4.00	0.00	AC	3.93	0.31	AC
6	Safety guide line and workshop safety	3.87	0.46		3.72	0.70	AC
7.	Properties building materials	3.03	0.45	MC	3.64	0.49	MC
8	Drawing instrument and materials	3.03	0.18	MC	3.65	0.47	MC
9	Board practice is and wood work tools	3.03	0.19		3.40	0.71	MC
10	Maintenance of tools and machine	3.00	0.09	MC	3.58	0.49	MC
11	Forces	3.03	0.18	MC	3.68	0.48	MC
12.	Chemicals	3.03	0.19	MC	3.58	0.51	MC
13.	Work, Energy and Power	3.29	0.80	MC	3.61	0.76	MC
14.	Types of Energy	3.95	0.23	AC	3.99	0.08	AC
15.	Thermal Energy	3.95	0.23	AC	3.99	0.08	AC
16.	Light Energy	3.81	0.52	AC	4.19	2.40	AC
17.	Crude oil and Petrochemicals	2.68	0.91	AC	2.37	1.01	AC
18.	Family traits	3.04	0.23	MC	2.91	0.34	MC
19.	Environmental Hazards I,II and III	3.03	0.17		2.97	0.25	MC
20.	Drug and substance abuse	3.96	0.18	AC	3.32	0.57	AC
21.	Resources from living things	3.46	0.72	MC	3.47	0.78	MC
22.	Resources from non-living things	3.11	0.33	MC	2.35	0.49	MC
23.	Sound Energy	3.13	0.36	MC	3.00	0.08	MC
24.	Magnetism	3.16	0.37	MC	2.35	0.49	MC
25.	Electrical Energy	3.13	0.42	MC	3.00	0.08	MC
26.	Radioactivity	3.12	0.42	MC	3.00	0.08	MC
27	Science and Development	3.08	0.36	MC	2.36	0.50	MC
	Sectional Mean	3.40	0.11	AC	3.38	0.13	AC

The analysis on table 4 indicated that urban Basic Science and Technology teachers had a sectional mean score of 3.40 with standard deviation of 0.11 while rural Basic Science and Technology teachers had a sectional mean score of 3.38 with standard deviation of 0.13, The mean difference between urban and rural basic science and technology teachers was 0.02 in favour of urban teachers, based on the acceptance limit of 2.50 mid-point on a 4-point rating scale. The result indicates that urban and rural Basic Science and Technology teachers did not differ in their level of coverage of the content for the implementation of Basic Science and Technology curriculum in upper basic schools in North central Nigeria.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Basic Science and Technology teachers regarding the common teaching methods used for curriculum implementation in Upper Basic Schools in North central Nigeria based on location.

Table 6: Summary of Mann Whitney U test Analysis on Use of recommended Teaching Method Used by Basic science and Technology teachers based on Location

Location	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Rank	Z	P	Remark
Urban	231	212.81	49,159.11	-4.215	0.001	Significant
Rural	155	164.73				

The result from the analysis on table 6, revealed that the mean rank scores were 212.81 and 164.73 for urban and rural Basic Science teachers respectively. Furthermore, the sum of mean ranks score was 49, 159.11 and 25, 533.15 for male and female Basic Science teachers respectively. Also the significant p-value of 0.001 was less than 0.05 level of significance. As a result, the first hypothesis was rejected. This show that there was significant difference in the response of urban and rural Basic Science and Technology teachers on teaching methods used for the implementation of Basic Science and Technology curriculum in Upper Basic Schools.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Basic Science and Technology teachers regarding the level of curriculum coverage content of Basic Science and Technology for implementation in Upper Basic Schools North central Nigeria based on location.

Table 6: Summary of Mann Whitney U test Analysis on Level of Coverage of Basic Science and Technology for Implementation of Basic Science and Technology Curriculum based on Location

Location	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Rank	Z	P	Remark
Urban	231	195.91	45, 255.21	0.523	0.601	Not significant
Rural	155	189.90	29, 434.5			

The result from the analysis on table 6, revealed that the mean rank scores were 195.91 and 189.90 for urban and rural Basic Science teachers respectively. Furthermore, the sum of mean ranks score was 45, 255.21 and 29, 434.5 for urban and rural Basic Science teachers respectively. Also the significant p-value of 0.601 was greater than 0.05 level of significance. As a result, the second hypothesis was accepted. This show that there is no significant difference in the response of urban and rural Basic Science and Technology teachers on the level of coverage of content of Basic Science and Technology curriculum for implementation in Upper Basic Schools

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding of the study revealed that teachers of Basic Science and Technology (BST) used variety of instructional strategies such as Active learning strategy, brainstorming, concept mapping, cooperative learning, demonstration, discovery method, discussion method, field trip or excursion method, lecture, problem-based learning, role play, guided discovery, project-based learning, team teaching, and using analogy have been identified as the common teaching methods. This finding is in line with the findings of Mohammed and Dajal (2024), Kayode (2020), Musa, Mahmuda and Kamba (2020) who reported that few teachers are utilizing these strategies effectively.

The findings of the study revealed that there was an adequate level of coverage of the content of Basic Science and Technology curriculum in Upper Basic Schools in North Central Nigeria. There is no significant difference in the response of urban and rural Basic Science and Technology teachers on the level of coverage of content of Basic Science and Technology curriculum for implementation in Upper

Basic Schools. This finding is consistent with Nagenu, Dajal and Apochi (2025), who reported that chemistry teachers in North Central Nigeria had high level of awareness and content coverage of the chemistry curriculum, irrespective of location.

CONCLUSION

The study found that the level of content coverage was generally adequate, with no location differences in their content coverage. In addition, teachers employed a different teaching methods which includes active learning, cooperative learning, and demonstration, with some differences between urban and rural teachers in the choice of methods.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made

1. Government through the school authorities should make serious effort to ensure that only the recommended instructional methods suitable for teaching and learning at various levels of education are utilized.
2. School administrators should ensure close monitoring of Basic Science and Technology teachers for implementing the appropriate teaching method in teaching Basic Science and Technology curriculum.
3. School administrators should ensure that the curriculum content must be adequately addressed, thus the focus should shift to enhancing the depth and quality of content delivery through interactive methods, utilisation of instructional materials, and regular oversight to ensure consistency in content coverage across various schools.
4. School administrators should ensure equal access to teaching resources and ongoing professional development to meet the needs of both urban and rural teachers in delivering the curriculum

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